

Perceived teaching styles as influencing factor of students' academic dishonesty

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This study examined whether students' perceptions of teacher strictness or leniency are associated with different forms of academic dishonesty. Using a descriptive-comparative design, data were collected from 301 university students across three colleges. Most respondents perceived their teachers as lenient and reported never engaging in cheating during exams, quizzes, or classroom activities. No significant differences were found in perceived teaching style across colleges, nor in exam-related cheating based on teaching style. However, significant differences emerged for plagiarism and the fabrication or falsification of academic papers, with higher self-reported engagement among students who perceived their teachers as strict. These findings suggest that perceived teaching style may be more relevant to dishonesty in written academic work than to in-class assessments. Educators may benefit from adopting autonomy-supportive approaches that balance structure with flexibility. Further research should incorporate teacher perspectives and formal class evaluation data to better understand mechanisms underlying academic misconduct.

Keywords: academic dishonesty; academic integrity; lenient teaching style; perceived teaching style; strict teaching style

Academic dishonesty remains a persistent concern in higher education, despite long-standing efforts to promote ethical conduct within educational institutions (Riad, 2023). Practices such as cheating, plagiarism, and the fabrication or falsification of academic work continue to challenge the integrity of assessment and learning outcomes (Mulenga & Shilongo, 2024). These concerns have prompted both symbolic and policy-level interventions aimed at reinforcing honesty as a core academic value.

One such symbolic effort is the widely cited maxim “Honesty is the best policy,” attributed to Sir Benjamin Franklin. In 2012, the Philippine House of Representatives passed a resolution requesting primary and secondary schools to display this quotation in all classrooms nationwide. The initiative was intended to promote good manners and right conduct among learners, reinforcing ethical behaviour throughout formal schooling and, ideally, into higher education (Department of Education, 2012). However, the continued prevalence of academic misconduct suggests that such measures, while well intentioned, may be insufficient on their own.

Academic dishonesty refers to behaviours such as cheating, plagiarism, fabrication or falsification, and sabotage (Baig & Arooj, 2025). Empirical evidence suggests that the prevalence of these behaviours has increased substantially over time. A nationwide statistical study conducted by the Educational Testing Service reported that approximately 20% of college students admitted to cheating in 1940, while more recent studies have documented markedly higher prevalence rates (Drake, 1941). This increase has been attributed to several factors, including shifts in learning modalities and the rapid expansion of modern technologies, which may have altered students’ perceptions of academic accountability and risk (Inamdar et al., 2021). These trends raise important questions about why students engage in academic dishonesty. While individual explanations such as fear of failure or lack of preparation have been widely discussed, increasing attention has been given to contextual influences within the classroom. Teachers play a central role in shaping students’ academic experiences (Alalid et al., 2025), and Blazar and Kraft (2017) indicate that teachers’ instructional practices and approaches can predict students’ classroom behaviour and attitudes, suggesting that teaching style may influence ethical decision-making.

Teachers are often regarded as influential authority figures whose behaviour contributes to the overall classroom climate (Debnam et al., 2023; Petřík & Vašašová, 2022; Relajo-Howell, 2024). Teaching styles perceived as lenient are commonly associated with approachability and emotional support, whereas strict teaching styles are often linked to control and high academic demands. However, strictness does not necessarily prevent academic dishonesty, especially when misconduct extends beyond examination cheating to include plagiarism and the fabrication or falsification of academic work. These inconsistencies raise a central question: What differences exist between lenient and strict teaching in relation to students’ engagement in academic dishonesty?

Guided by students’ perspectives, this study employs a descriptive-comparative research design to examine whether perceived teaching style is associated with differences in academic dishonesty among university students across different colleges at a public higher education institution in the Philippines. The findings aim to contribute empirical evidence to discussions on teaching practices and academic integrity and to inform research-based approaches to addressing academic misconduct in higher education.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The study employed a descriptive-comparative research design to examine differences in students' self-reported academic dishonesty based on their perceived teaching style. Specifically, the design was used to compare levels of academic dishonesty among students from three colleges of Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology (NEUST) according to whether their advisory teacher was perceived as lenient or strict. Descriptive-comparative designs aim to describe and compare existing differences among groups without manipulation of variables (Cantrell, 2011; Devi, 2023;).

Students' perceptions of their advisory teacher's teaching style were used to categorise respondents into two groups: lenient or strict, based on the dominant teaching style perceived. The design allowed for the examination of differences in perceived teaching style across colleges, as well as differences in academic dishonesty based on teaching style.

Research participants

The respondents were undergraduate students enrolled during the first semester of the academic year 2023–2024 at NEUST. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select respondents from three colleges. A total of 301 students participated in the study. One hundred respondents were drawn from the College of Arts and Sciences, one hundred from the College of Nursing, and one hundred one from the College of Engineering. Students were eligible to participate if they were currently enrolled and had an identified advisory teacher at the time of data collection.

Instrumentation

The study utilised a structured survey questionnaire composed of three sections. The first section collected demographic information, specifically the respondents' college affiliation. The second section measured perceived teaching style. This instrument consisted of 20 items developed by the researchers to reflect lenient and strict teaching behaviours. Responses were recorded using a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 4 (Strongly Agree) to 1 (Strongly Disagree). The scale was designed to identify whether respondents perceived their advisory teacher as predominantly lenient or strict. Cronbach's alpha was computed to assess the internal consistency of the teaching style items. Items with low reliability were revised and revalidated to improve the overall reliability of the scale. The third section measured academic dishonesty. An adapted and modified version of the academic dishonesty questionnaire developed by Quintos (2017) was used. The instrument consisted of 24 items assessing the self-reported frequency of engagement in academically dishonest behaviours. Responses were recorded on a 4-point Likert scale, where 4 indicated six times or more, 3 indicated four to five times, 2 indicated one to three times, and 1 indicated never. Cronbach's alpha was also computed to assess the reliability of the modified academic dishonesty scale.

Data collection procedure

Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the deans of the participating colleges, and informed consent was secured from all respondents prior to data collection. Questionnaires were administered both in person using a pen-and-paper format and online using Google Forms.

For face-to-face administration, questionnaires were distributed and collected on the same day. For online administration, the survey link was disseminated to students within the selected colleges. Clear instructions were provided prior to completion, and respondents were given the opportunity to seek

clarification from the researchers during administration. All questionnaires were checked for completeness before inclusion in the final analysis.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used to summarise respondents’ demographic profiles by college. Weighted means and corresponding verbal interpretations were computed to describe perceived teaching style and levels of academic dishonesty.

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine whether there were significant differences in perceived teaching style when respondents were grouped according to college. Independent samples t-tests, with Levene’s test for equality of variances, were used to examine differences in academic dishonesty based on perceived teaching style. Statistical significance was evaluated using conventional thresholds.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents by college. Of the 301 respondents, 101 (34%) were from the College of Engineering, while 100 respondents each (33%) were from the College of Arts and Sciences and the College of Nursing.

Table 1
 Demographic distribution of student respondents by college

College	N	n	%
College of Arts and Sciences (CAS)	760	100	33%
College of Engineering (COE)	3000	101	34%
College of Nursing (CON)	1140	100	33%
Total	4900	301	100%

Table 2 presents the weighted means and verbal interpretations of respondents’ perceptions of their teachers’ strict teaching style. Overall, respondents generally disagreed that their teachers employed a strict teaching style (AWM = 2.30). The highest-rated item was teachers’ expectation that students be serious in learning course materials (M = 3.09), while the lowest-rated item concerned teacher irritation when students asked questions (M = 1.49).

Table 2
 Students' perceived teaching style (strict)

Strict teaching style items	WM	Description
1. My advisory teacher underestimates my ability to perform in exams, exercises, or quizzes.	1.82	Disagree
2. My advisory teacher displays clear authority in the classroom.	2.74	Agree
3. My advisory teacher often says that I am lacking and should make more effort in my studies.	2.12	Disagree
4. My advisory teacher insists that I complete tasks according to their expectations.	2.65	Agree
5. When my advisory teacher assigns a task, they expect it to be completed immediately and submitted on time.	2.75	Agree
6. My advisory teacher's decision is final even with some clarifications.	2.57	Agree
7. My advisory teacher gets upset when students disagree with their ideas about the lessons.	1.76	Disagree
8. The teacher expects me to be serious in learning from the materials that is intended to my course.	3.09	Agree
9. When I complain about getting low scores on quizzes and tests, my teacher tells me that it is my fault.	2.03	Disagree
10. My teacher gets irritated whenever I ask questions related to lessons, activities, exams, or quizzes.	1.49	Strongly Disagree
AWM	2.30	Disagree

Note: 1.00–1.74 = Strongly disagree; 1.75–2.49 = Disagree; 2.50–3.24 = Agree; 3.25–4.00 = Strongly agree

Table 3 presents the weighted means and verbal interpretations of respondents' perceptions of their teachers' lenient teaching style. Overall, respondents agreed that their teachers employed a lenient teaching style (AWM = 2.99). The highest-rated items reflected teacher approachability and openness to questions ($M = 3.42$), while the lowest-rated item concerned allowance of late submission of schoolwork ($M = 2.34$).

Table 3
 Students' perceived teaching style (lenient)

Lenient teaching style items	WM	Description
1. My teacher provides reviewers or the materials of our lessons before the discussion.	3.12	Agree
2. My teacher provides activities and tasks with enough time before deadline.	3.22	Agree
3. My advisory teacher allows me to behave the way I want in class.	2.66	Agree
4. My advisory teacher is lenient with grades even without putting in so much effort.	2.39	Disagree
5. My advisory teacher ensures a comfortable learning environment (laid back and relaxed).	2.97	Agree
6. My advisory teacher is very easy to get along with in class.	3.25	Strongly Agree
7. My advisory teacher is approachable in asking questions.	3.42	Strongly Agree
8. My advisory teacher is very considerate and comfortable to talk with.	3.28	Strongly Agree
9. My advisory teacher allows late submission of projects and other schoolwork.	2.34	Disagree
10. My advisory teacher accepts suggestions or opinions from students.	3.27	Strongly Agree
AWM	2.99	Agree

Note: 1.00–1.74 = Strongly disagree; 1.75–2.49 = Disagree; 2.50–3.24 = Agree; 3.25–4.00 = Strongly agree

Table 4 presents the weighted means and verbal interpretations of respondents' self-reported frequency of cheating during exams, quizzes, and classroom activities. Overall, respondents reported never engaging in cheating behaviours (AWM = 1.51). The most frequently reported behaviour was noticing another student cheating without reporting it ($M = 2.25$), while the least frequently reported behaviours involved the use of cheat notes or leaving the examination room to obtain answers ($M = 1.14$).

Table 4
 Academic dishonesty in terms of cheating in exam, quizzes, and activities

Cheating in exams and assessments	WM	Description
1. I asked another student for questions or answers from an exam, exercise, or quiz they had previously taken.	1.79	1–3 times
2. I gave another student questions or answers from an exam, exercise, or quiz I had previously taken.	1.80	1–3 times
3. I copied answers from another student during an exam, exercise, or quiz.	1.70	Never
4. I allowed another student to copy my answers during an exam, exercise, or quiz.	1.96	1–3 times
5. I used a cheat note during an exam, exercise, or quiz.	1.14	Never
6. I changed an answer after an exam, exercise, or quiz was graded and then reported a grading error.	1.15	Never
7. I noticed another student cheating during an exam, exercise, or quiz and did not report it.	2.25	1–3 times
8. I noticed that my teacher mistakenly marked one of my incorrect answers as correct and did not report it.	1.48	Never
9. I used a phone or computer to transmit answers to another student during an exam, exercise, or quiz.	1.28	Never
10. I used a phone or computer to ask someone for answers during an exam, exercise, or quiz, including departmental assessments.	1.27	Never
11. I opened my manual, notes, or reference book during an exam, exercise, or quiz when it was not permitted and the teacher or proctor was away.	1.19	Never
12. I excused myself during an exam, exercise, or quiz to obtain answers from someone outside.	1.14	Never
AWM	1.51	Never

Note: 1–1.74 = Never; 1.75–2.49 = One to three times; 2.50–3.24 = 4–5 times; 3.25–4.00 = 6 times and above

Table 5 presents the weighted means and verbal interpretations of respondents' self-reported frequency of plagiarism and fabrication or falsification in academic papers. Overall, respondents reported never engaging in these behaviours (AWM = 1.51). The most frequently reported behaviour was making up sources or citations ($M = 1.75$), while the least frequently reported behaviours involved asking another person to complete academic work or submitting the same paper in multiple classes ($M = 1.29$).

Table 5

Academic dishonesty in terms of plagiarism and fabrication or falsification in academic paper

Plagiarism and fabrication	WM	Description
1. I made up sources or citations for my paper requirements.	1.75	1–3 times
2. I fabricated results for a laboratory experiment, activity, or research task assigned to me.	1.49	Never
3. I altered the results of a laboratory experiment, activity, or project when the desired results were not obtained.	1.48	Never
4. I copied a work from the Internet or a journal and I presented it as my own original work.	1.37	Never
5. I took ideas from others and used them in my research or activities without giving credit to the original author.	1.40	Never
6. I had another person write a paper, project, or academic output that I have then presented as my own work.	1.29	Never
7. I wrote a paper, project, or academic output for another person that they then presented as their own work	1.53	Never
8. I turned-in the same paper in two different classes without making sure it is alright with the teachers.	1.29	Never
9. I copy-pasted materials from the Internet in writing a paper.	1.65	Never
10. I worked with a group in a paper that was assigned as individual work	1.62	Never
11. I took someone else’s paper or copy a paper from a journal or the Internet, then paraphrased the contents and presented it as my own.	1.53	Never
12. I intentionally quoted a part of a journal/reference out of its original context to use it in support of my argument in a paper.	1.71	Never
AWM	1.51	Never

Note: 1–1.74 = Never; 1.75–2.49 = 1–3 times; 2.50-3.24 = 4–5 times; 3.25–4.00 = 6times and above

Table 6 presents the results of the one-way analysis of variance examining differences in perceived teaching style when respondents were grouped according to college. No significant differences were found for strict teaching style ($F = 2.714, p = 0.068$) or lenient teaching style ($F = 1.270, p = 0.282$).

Table 6

ANOVA of the perceived teaching style according to college

	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Strict Teaching Style	2.714	0.068
Lenient Teaching Style	1.270	0.282

* $p < .05$

Table 7 presents the results of the independent samples t-tests examining differences in academic dishonesty based on perceived teaching style. No significant difference was found in cheating during exams, quizzes, and activities ($F = 2.184, p = 0.141$). However, a significant difference was found in plagiarism and fabrication or falsification in academic papers ($F = 4.468, p = 0.035$), with higher mean scores among respondents who perceived their teachers as strict.

Table 7

Independent sample test of academic dishonesty according to teachers' teaching style using Levene's test

	TS	N	M	F	Sig.
Cheating in exam, quizzes, and activities	ST	64	1.6328	2.184	0.141
	LT	237	1.4787		
Plagiarism and fabrication or falsification in academic paper	ST	64	1.6339	4.468	0.035
	LT	237	1.4751		

Note: TS = Teaching Style; ST = Strict Teaching Style; LT = Lenient Teaching Style

* $p < .05$

DISCUSSION

This study examined whether students' perceptions of teachers' strictness or leniency are associated with differences in academic dishonesty. The findings indicate that, overall, students reported low levels of academic dishonesty, particularly in relation to cheating during exams, quizzes, and classroom activities. Similar patterns have been reported in previous studies suggesting that students often demonstrate academic self-efficacy and autonomy in formal assessment contexts, which may reduce the likelihood of overt cheating (Anthonysamy & Singh, 2025; Clare & Curtis, 2023; Putarek & Pavlin-Bernardić, 2020).

Consistent with the results, no significant difference was found in cheating during exams, quizzes, and classroom activities between students who perceived their teachers as strict and those who perceived their teachers as lenient. This suggests that overt forms of cheating may be influenced by factors other than teaching style, such as assessment conditions, supervision, or students' personal standards. Prior research has similarly indicated that cheating behaviour is frequently shaped by situational and institutional controls rather than instructor leniency alone, including exam difficulty, preparedness, and time pressure (Fatima & Hosny, 2014).

In contrast, a significant difference was observed in plagiarism and the fabrication or falsification of academic papers based on perceived teaching style. Students who perceived their teachers as strict reported higher levels of engagement in these forms of academic dishonesty compared with those who perceived their teachers as lenient. This finding aligns with earlier research showing that academic dishonesty is more prevalent in written assignments and projects than in examinations, where monitoring is more direct (Alguacil et al., 2024; Hossain & Nurunnabi, 2018; Quintos, 2017).

One possible explanation for this pattern is that strict teaching styles may heighten students' perceptions of pressure, particularly in relation to deadlines, performance expectations, and evaluation of written work. When academic demands are perceived as rigid or punitive, students may be more inclined to engage in plagiarism or fabrication as coping strategies to meet requirements rather than risk failure. Conversely, lenient or autonomy-supportive teaching styles may reduce perceived pressure and foster psychological comfort, allowing students to engage more authentically with academic tasks (Angkiko, 2016).

This interpretation is supported by research indicating that autonomy-supportive teaching styles are associated with higher levels of student motivation and engagement, whereas controlling or authoritarian approaches may undermine self-determined motivation (Ali & Inayat, 2020; Amoura et al., 2015; Coterón et al., 2024). Studies drawing on Self-determination Theory suggest that when students perceive greater autonomy and support from instructors, they are more likely to internalise academic values, which may reduce the likelihood of engaging in dishonest practices, particularly in

tasks requiring independent effort such as writing assignments (Bassett et al., 2013; Šimon & Pavlin-Bernardić, 2024; Walker, 2008).

The present findings also help explain why no significant differences were observed in exam-related cheating. In structured assessment settings such as examinations and quizzes, opportunities for cheating may be limited by supervision, time constraints, and assessment design. As a result, students' behaviour in these contexts may be less influenced by perceived teaching style and more shaped by situational controls and institutional rules, consistent with prior evidence on the role of punitive consequences and monitoring in discouraging cheating (Chirikov et al., 2019; Clare & Curtis, 2023; Humbert et al., 2022).

Despite generally low self-reported levels of academic dishonesty, passive forms of misconduct, such as noticing cheating without reporting it, were more common than direct engagement in cheating. This pattern mirrors findings by Arimi and Starovoytova (2016), who reported widespread reluctance among students to report peers' dishonest behaviour. Such reluctance may reflect social norms, fear of retaliation, or stigma associated with whistle-blowing, rather than endorsement of cheating itself.

These findings should be interpreted considering several limitations. Academic dishonesty was measured using self-report data, which may be influenced by social desirability or underreporting. Teaching style was also assessed based on students' perceptions rather than direct observation, which may reflect individual biases. In addition, the cross-sectional design limits causal interpretation, as associations between perceived teaching style and academic dishonesty cannot be assumed to indicate directionality.

Despite these limitations, the study contributes to the growing body of research examining contextual influences on academic dishonesty in higher education. By distinguishing between different forms of academic misconduct and examining them in relation to perceived teaching style, the findings highlight the importance of instructional approaches that balance academic standards with supportive learning environments. These results underscore the role of teachers not only in enforcing rules, but also in shaping the motivational climate that may influence students' ethical academic behaviour.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between students' perceptions of teachers' strictness or leniency and different forms of academic dishonesty among university students. Overall, the findings indicate that students reported low levels of direct academic dishonesty, particularly in relation to cheating during exams, quizzes, and classroom activities. However, the results also reveal that academic dishonesty is not absent, with passive behaviours such as failing to report observed cheating and certain forms of plagiarism occurring more frequently than overt cheating.

Importantly, while no significant differences were found in exam-related cheating based on perceived teaching style, a significant difference emerged in relation to plagiarism and the fabrication or falsification of academic papers. Students who perceived their teachers as strict reported higher engagement in these forms of academic dishonesty compared with those who perceived their teachers as lenient. This suggests that perceived teaching style may play a more salient role in students' ethical behaviour in written academic tasks than in highly structured and supervised assessment contexts.

The findings contribute to the growing literature on academic dishonesty by highlighting the importance of distinguishing between different types of misconduct rather than treating academic dishonesty as a single, uniform behaviour. They also underscore the relevance of instructional context,

particularly students' perceptions of teaching style, in shaping how academic demands are navigated. While strict approaches may be intended to promote discipline and performance, they may inadvertently increase pressure in ways that encourage dishonest practices in less regulated academic tasks.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The study relied on self-reported data, which may be influenced by social desirability bias, and teaching style was assessed from the students' perspective rather than through direct observation. In addition, the cross-sectional design limits causal interpretation. Future research would benefit from including teachers' perspectives, employing mixed-methods approaches, and examining a broader range of teaching styles across more diverse institutional contexts.

Despite these limitations, the study offers practical and theoretical insight into how perceived teaching practices relate to academic dishonesty. By emphasising the role of supportive and autonomy-oriented instructional environments, the findings suggest that promoting academic integrity may require not only clear rules and consequences, but also teaching approaches that foster motivation, engagement, and ethical responsibility among students.

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